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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЗАЩИТЫ ПРАВ ЧЕЛОВЕКА В КОНТЕКСТЕ МИРОВОГО СОГЛАШЕНИЯ ЕВРОПЕЙСКОГО СУДА ПО ПРАВАМ ЧЕЛОВЕКА

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PECULIARITIES OF HUMAN RIGHTS PROTECTION IN THE CONTEXT OF THE FRIENDLY- SETTLEMENT OF THE EUROPEAN COURT OF HUMAN RIGHTS

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Аннотация

В данной научной статье, на основании изучения мнений известных правоведов, международных документов по правам человека, Европейской конвенции о защите прав человека и основных свобод, Регламента Европейского суда по правам человека представлены особенности защиты прав человека на этапе заключения мирного соглашения сторонами. Более того, в статье также рассматриваются проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются Суд и стороны на этапе реализации мирного соглашения. Наряду с этим, автор раскрывает особенности понятий “права человека” и “мирное соглашение”.

Abstract

In this scientific article, based on the study of the opinions of famous legal scholars, international human rights documents, the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and the Rules of the European Court of Human Rights, the features of human rights protection at the stage of concluding a friendly-settlement by the parties are presented. Moreover, the article also examines the problems that the Court and the parties face at the stage of implementing a friendly-settlement. Besides, the author reveals the features of the concepts of “human rights” and “peace agreement”.

Ключевые слова: права человек, мировое соглашение, Европейский Суд по правам человека, международное гуманитарное право, государство, Регламент суда.

Keywords: human rights, friendly-settlement, European Court of Human Rights, international humanitarian law, state, Rules of Court.

The guarantee and protection of human rights and freedoms is one of the primary functions of a modern democratic, legal, and social state.

According to the universally recognized definition, human rights are an opportunity to determine the extent of one's own behavior. All other persons, public authorities, organizations must refrain from interfering with this behavior [3, p.12;6].

It should be noted, that the idea of creating inter-governmental organizations for the protection of fundamental human rights and freedoms was based on the desire to ensure the protection of human rights and freedoms in cases where the State has violated human rights and freedoms, and domestic measures have not ensured their protection and restoration. In other words, in order to protect and restore violated human rights, an independent judicial body should have been created in which justice and protection from the arbitrariness of

national courts, officials and laws could be found. Such a body is the European Court of Human Rights (hereinafter also referred to as the Court, the European Court, the ECHR). It is known that the European Court is an independent judicial body established on the basis of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (hereinafter also referred to as the European Convention, the Convention) and has the authority to examine disputes related to violations of human rights and freedoms in the member states of the Council of Europe, as well as to prevent similar cases in the future. According to E. E. Ampleeva, and V. V. Firsov, the European Convention became the first official international agreement of the Council of Europe aimed at protecting human rights. Moreover, it is the first international agreement with an effective mechanism for its implementation, since any international agreement or contract, especially in the field of

human rights, risks remaining an empty declaration if an effective system for the implementation of international obligations for the participating states is not developed [1,p.13].

It is noteworthy, that the European Court of Human Rights is an international judicial body whose jurisdiction extends to all member states of the Council of Europe that have ratified the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms. Its jurisdiction covers all questions concerning the interpretation and application of the Convention, including Inter-State and individual applications [27,17-18].

In this regard, a remarkable point of view is presented in the legal literature by A. Reidy, D. Weissbrodt and P. Hicks according to which the Convention is applicable with respect to the acts or omissions of any Contracting Party during an armed conflict, if it is a matter of State responsibility of the Contracting Party. This includes responsibility for acts or omissions during an armed conflict within the national territory of a State Party, as well as actions undertaken by its armed forces outside its national territory [8; 28].

In its turn, H. Grigoryan rightly pointed out that international humanitarian law establishes a direct dependence of the qualifications of aggression and other war crimes on the nature of the armed conflict, recognizing similar acts, in some cases, as military and other international crimes, but not in others [5].

Within the framework of the topic under discussion, it is worth noting that legal experts have repeatedly emphasized the importance of the decisions of the European Court in the procedure for interpreting and applying the Convention. In other words, the European Court, through its interpretations (comments) determines the only possible and correct meaning and content of the Convention, as well as its norms and legal concepts [2;7].

The conducted research shows, that the problem of human rights protection of human rights protection can also arise in the European Court of Human Rights, not only during the examination of the case, but also at the stage of a friendly-settlement. Generally the friendly-settlement procedure applied by the Court initially resolves a number of issues related to the alleged violation of human rights and gives the applicant an opportunity to quickly resolve the issue of compensation. Moreover, the friendly-settlement is an agreement between the parties, which is very similar to an out-of-court settlement under domestic law and allows the parties to resolve the case, usually on the basis of a payment of a certain amount (judge satisfaction) to the applicant, a promise to take certain actions to resolve the issue, or a combination of the two.

According to Rule 62¹ of the Rule of European Court of Human rights (hereinafter referred to as the Rule of Court, Rules of the European Court), after declaring an application admissible, the Registrar, acting on the instructions of the Chamber or its President, shall enter into contact with the parties with a view to securing a friendly-settlement of the matter in accordance with Article 39 § 1 of the Convention. The Chamber shall take all appropriate steps to facilitate such a settlement [26].

It is noteworthy, that this process usually refers to the stage of communication. It is usually at this point that the Registrar tries to ensure the conclusion of a friendly-settlement. He or she may offer the parties an amount commensurate with the seriousness of the alleged violation and corresponding to the amounts awarded by the Court in similar cases for pecuniary and non-pecuniary damage [9,p.87-88].

Furthermore, under Article 39 § 1 of the Convention, the Court may, at any stage of the proceedings, provide assistance to the parties to the case with a view to securing a friendly-settlement of the case on the basis of respect for the rights set forth in the Convention and its Protocols [4].

The conducted research shows, that *the issue of human rights protection in the ECHR can also arise during the negotiation stage, for a number of reasons.*

First of all, the European Court notes in its decisions that friendly-settlement negotiations are confidential and that a violation of this condition may lead to the Court declaring the application inadmissible on the basis of abuse of the right to apply to the Court. Thus, the violation of confidentiality by one of the parties leads to unfavorable conditions in the context of human rights [14;17].

The main purpose of “confidentiality” is to facilitate the conclusion of a settlement agreement and to ensure that offers made during negotiations are not disclosed and made public.

The Court has repeatedly noted in its decisions, that the rule of confidentiality protects the activities of the court, including its impartiality. Moreover, this principle guarantees, that in case of failure of negotiations on a friendly-settlement agreement, their content will not affect the outcome of the proceedings [12; 13;17;20;25]. The rule of confidentiality also serves to protect both the parties and the Court from any attempts to exert political or other pressure on them.

The European Court has stressed that the rule of confidentiality is “absolute” [18]. A breach of this rule may, in certain circumstances, constitute an abuse of the right of individual application to the Court and lead to its being declared inadmissible under Article 35 § 3 (a) of the Convention.

Second, the Court sets time limits for the parties to submit proposals, which can be extended by a party. However, the time limit can also be extended by the European Court, which is often actively involved in facilitating friendly-settlements. Moreover, the Court may decide to strike an application out of its list of cases if the applicant has “unjustly”, “baseless” rejected friendly-settlement proposals. For instance, when financial negotiations reach an impasse, the court may suggest what amount of money it would be reasonable to pay to settle the case [16].

Moreover, the court takes any measures for negotiations and a positive conclusion, including organizing meetings and discussions between the parties. **Consequently, the problem of human rights protection also arises when a court considers a refusal to be “unjustified” and removes a case from the list for consideration.**

At the same time, we agree with the opinion of legal scholars, that the ECHR has the right to accept or reject the parties' agreement on a friendly-settlement, which means that the judges have the final say, and they bear ultimate responsibility for the fulfillment of human rights and obligations, and the emergence of a problem with the protection of human rights [24].

Our studies show that the Court is most inclined to resolve the case through a friendly- settlement, in order to relieve the Court's workload and facilitate its activities.

If the conditions presented by the ECHR are acceptable to both parties, the parties must notify the court in writing of their approval of the terms of the friendly-settlement and request that the case be removed from the Court's list of cases. *In that case, the Court will issue a decision or judgment, recording the factual circumstances of the case and the terms agreed between the parties, and officially exclude the case from the Court's list of cases [4].*

However, after obtaining the agreement between the parties, before striking the application (case) out of the Court's list of cases, the Court examines whether the agreement was concluded on the basis of respect for human rights and will not lead to similar violations in the future.

If the court has any doubts that the agreement may result in a violation of human rights, or if there is no certainty that the applicant has agreed to the terms of the friendly-settlement, the European Court shall continue the further examination of the application on its merits [19;22].

It should be noted, that if the terms of the friendly-settlement are not fulfilled, the submitted application will be reviewed again in the European Court [15]. Although current procedure was introduced with the adoption of Protocol №11 to the European Convention, it has been ameliorated by Protocol №14.

It is noteworthy, that when an attempt at a friendly-settlement has failed, that is, the parties have not reached an agreement, one of the parties is entitled **to make a unilateral declaration**. *Particularly, according to Rule 62 of the Rules of the European Court, if the applicant has refused the terms of the proposed friendly-settlement, the respondent State may file with the Court a request to strike the application out of the list. Moreover, the request shall be accompanied by a declaration clearly acknowledging that there has been a violation of the Convention in the applicant's case together with an undertaking to provide adequate redress and, as appropriate, to take necessary remedial measures [26].*

This application is submitted within the framework of public and adversarial proceedings conducted separately from the friendly-settlement proceeding and with due respect for the confidentiality of this proceeding.

According to Rule of Court and judgments of ECHR, even if the applicant wishes the examination of the application to continue, the Court may strike it out of the list (either in whole or in part), if it considers that the declaration offers a sufficient basis for finding that respect for human rights as defined in the Convention

and the Protocols thereto does not require it to continue its examination of the application [11;21;23;26].

Thus, there are no substantiated facts that will allow continuing the investigation of the case and not signing a friendly-settlement.

The conducted research shows, that in order for the Court to cease the examination of a case on the basis of a unilateral declaration and remove it from the list, it is necessary that it meets certain criteria, such as respect for human rights, the existence of established case law on the issue raised in the application, a clear recognition of the fact of a violation of the European Convention against the applicant with an exact indication of the nature of the violation, etc. Otherwise, the European Court is obliged to continue the examination of the case.

A vivid example of this is the "Case of Safaryan v. Armenia", in which the State proposed to ratify the friendly-settlement agreement and requested the Court to strike the application from the list of cases. Simultaneously, the applicant objected to the State's request to strike the application out of the list of cases and requested that the Court continue the examination of the application on the merits, since the Government's statement did not cover all of his complaints and that no redress had been offered by the State. In turn, the Government failed to provide sufficient sufficient evidence of respect for substantive human rights, and in the circumstances the Court continued to examine the merits of the case[21].

It is worth noting that the issue of human rights protection may also arise during the implementation of friendly-settlement agreements and unilateral declarations.

In other words, despite the fact that the application of friendly-settlements and unilateral declarations contribute to the rapid restoration of violated human rights, nevertheless, certain difficulties associated with the implementation of these processes may arise in domestic law enforcement practice.

A problem related to the enforcement of a court decision may arise if the domestic courts do not have clearly defined procedures for reviewing or reopening judicial acts that have entered into force on such grounds. In this case, the position of ECHR is again ambiguous. For instance, in the case of Jeronović v. Latvia, the Court struck out the application from the list of cases, based on the unilateral declaration by the State, and already at the domestic level the applicant requested the reopening of the case[13]. The case was not pursued at the domestic level, as the Government argued that there was no such possibility in the domestic legal system. Moreover, the ECHR did not envisage such a procedure within the framework of the given case.

Subsequently, the European Court, considering the justification provided by the State inadmissible, restored the application to the list of cases and issued a judgment finding a violation. In that Judgment, the Court reaffirmed the previously established standard, that in case of a procedural violation, the State is obliged to conduct an effective examination of the case,

and the refusal to reopen the case in domestic courts contradicts European standards [13].

The Republic of Armenia faced a similar problem in the context of the “Case of Ashot Grigoryan and Others v. Armenia”, when ECHR while upholding the unilateral declaration made by the Government of the Republic of Armenia, did not in any way address the legislative possibility of review by domestic judicial bodies that basis [10]

Based on the systematic analysis of the above-mentioned judicial precedents, we can conclude that the European Court of Human Rights applies double standards. In one case, the court rejected the unilateral declaration, arguing that there was no mechanism in the domestic legal system for reopening the case, and in the other case, it accepted the unilateral declaration made and made a decision on it. Moreover, considering that unilateral declaration, as well as friendly-settlement, as a new circumstance is conditioned by the interpretations made by the courts in this regard. That is, in one case, the judicial bodies of a particular state may apply the provision on the review of a judicial act on the basis of a new circumstance more broadly, also allowing the review of the case on the basis of decisions made on the basis of a unilateral declaration and friendly-settlement, and in another, narrower case, applying exclusively the grounds provided for by the legislator.

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